

Phytochemical Investigation of *Borreria articularis* Linn.

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Borreria articularis Linn. (Rubiaceae)^{1,2} is a herb occurring abundantly in the temperate region of India. It grows widely in and around Santiniketan and is locally used as folk medicine. Literature revealed that no phytochemical work has yet been reported on this plant. A systematic chemical examination of the whole plants (aerial parts and roots) was, therefore, undertaken and the results are reported.

Are-dried powdered whole plants (aerial parts and roots) of *B. articularis* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) benzene and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silicagel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene (1 : 3) mixture afforded a solid, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (*m/z* 442), m.p. 232°; responded positive in Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 480 (OH), 1 645 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation), acetate, m.p. 185°. It was characterised as erythrodiol by m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir determination with authentic sample³.

The concentrated benzene extract upon chromatographic resolution over silicagel yielded a compound with benzene-chloroform (3 : 1) mixture which after crystallisation from benzene furnished a solid, C₃₀H₄₆O₃ (**1**), m.p. 22–25°, [α]_D³⁰ + 80° (CHCl₃); responded to Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 710 (C=O), 1 700 (COOH) and 1 645 cm⁻¹ (unsaturation); the triterpene afforded a methyl ester, C₃₁H₄₈O₃ (**2**), m.p. 156–58°, [α]_D³⁰+78° (CHCl₃) on boiling with 5% methanolic HCl for 20 h. This methyl ester readily formed 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 210–12°. The ¹H

nmr spectrum (90 MHz ; CDCl₃) of the parent triterpene displayed signals at δ 0.75 (3H, s), 0.80 (3H, s), 0.88 (3H, s), 0.93 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), and 1.25 (6H, s) for seven tertiary methyls, two protons multiplet around δ 2.30 (COCH₂) and one vinylic proton at δ 5.25.

The mass fragmentation pattern of the compound is similar to Δ^{12} -oleanene type of pentacyclic triterpene⁴ and its mass spectrum records significant peaks at *m/z* 454 (*M*⁺), 248 (base peak), 205 (r.D.A fragmentation around ring-C), 233 (248-CH₃) and 203 (248-COOH). From the above mass fragmentation pattern it is evident that the keto group in the triterpene is present in A/B-ring portion and its location at C₃ is highly probable from biogenetic consideration as well as from the positive Zimmermann test. Further, the appearance of the mass peak at *m/z* 248 as the base peak reveals that the carboxyl group is located in the portion containing D/E-rings.

Finally, the methyl ester (**2**) of this triterpene on reduction with NaBH₄ furnished a triterpene, C₃₁H₅₀O₃ (**3**), m.p. 200°, [α]_D³⁰ + 55° (CHCl₃), the acetate, 240–45°, which was identified as methyl epikatonate⁵ (olean-12-en-3 β -ol-29-methyl carboxylate) by comparison of physical constants. This conclusively establishes the structure of the triterpene as 3-keto-olean-12-en-29-oic acid (**1**) which appears to be the first report of occurrence of this triterpene from natural source.

The concentrated chloroform extract on usual chromatography over silicagel furnished β -sitosterol and n-hentriacontanol in petroleum ether (b.p. 6080°)–benzene (1 : 1) eluate while benzene-chloroform

(1 : 3) eluate yielded a triterpene, $C_{30}H_{48}O_3$, (M^+ 456), m.p. 260–62°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 50^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$); ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 1690 (COOH) and 1650 cm^{-1} (unsaturation). The triterpene on boiling with 5% methanolic HCl furnished a methyl ester, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 200°, which was found to be com-

pletely identical with the methyl epikatonate (3)⁵ by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) characterising the triterpene as epikatonic acid (olean-12-en-3 β -ol-29-oic acid; 4).

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